

CEDEFOP

European Centre for the Development
of Vocational Training

Early school leaving in the EU: main concerns and possible actions from the EU institutions

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**Spring Meeting of the COMECE Commission on Culture
and Education, 16.5.2025 online**

Who we are

- We are one of the first 'decentralised' EU agencies
- Specialising in **vocational education and training (VET), skills and qualifications policy**
- Set up in 1975 in Berlin, founded upon the initiative of the European Economic and Social Committee
- Moved to Thessaloniki in 1995

Cedefop in the institutional environment

DG Employment =
Cedefop's partner DG

Cedefop's 'sister' agencies:

What Cedefop does

Working together with the Commission, Member States and social partners

We help design, promote and realise VET, skills and qualifications policy, by:

- analysing and researching into
 - labour markets' changing skill needs
 - VET policies and their developments in the Member States
- providing evidence for policy-making
- helping countries learn from each other

Cedefop's work on inclusion

Our mission

**Making VET systems
and labour markets
inclusive**

VET4YOUTH TEAM

PROMOTING INCLUSIVE EXCELLENCE FOR YOUNG PEOPLE

INCLUSION

Tackling early leaving
from VET

Empowering young
NEETs

Professional
development of VET
teachers & trainers

EXCELLENCE

Digital skills in IVET
provision

EU PILLAR OF SOCIAL
RIGHTS 2030

DIGITAL EDUCATION ACTION
PLAN 2021-2027

SUPPORTING EU POLICY FRAMEWORK

- Council recommendation on Pathways to School Success
- Council conclusions on European teachers and trainers for the future
- Council recommendation on improving the provision of digital skills in E&T

In 2023 9.5 % of 18–24-year-olds in the EU had completed at most, a lower secondary education and were not in further education or training (early leavers)

Early leavers from education and training, 2023

(% of population aged 18-24)

Croatia and Slovenia: break in time series; Croatia and Luxembourg: low reliability.

The overall share of early leavers from education and training fell in the EU by 2.3 pp between 2013 and 2023

Early leavers from education and training, 2013 and 2023

(% of population aged 18-24)

Note: break in time series.

(*) 2023: Low reliability.

Source: Eurostat (online data code: edat_ifse_14)

A higher proportion by 3.6 pp of early leavers are men

Early leavers from education and training by sex, 2023

(% of population aged 18-24)

Note: ranked on overall share of early leavers (young men and women); breaks in series.

(*) Low reliability.

(*) Young men and young women: low reliability.

(*) Young women: low reliability.

Source: Eurostat (online data code: edat_lfse_14)

In 2023, 52.6 % of early leavers were not employed

Distribution of early leavers from education and training by labour status, 2023

(% of early leavers aged 18-24)

Note: ranked on share of employed early leavers. Luxembourg is not available.

(*) Low reliability.

(?) Not wanting to work and would like to work: low reliability.

(*) Would like to work: low reliability.

(*) Not wanting to work: low reliability.

(*) Employed: low reliability.

(*) Would like to work and not wanting to work: not available due to a very low reliability. 'Would like to work' refers to 'Not employed'.

Source: Eurostat (online data code: edat_ifse_14)

Cedefop research on inclusion

Leaving education early:
putting vocational education
and training centre stage

Volume I: investigating causes and extent

Leaving education early:
putting vocational education
and training centre stage

Volume II: evaluating policy impact

DOI: [10.2801/757603](https://doi.org/10.2801/757603)

DOI: [10.2801/75320](https://doi.org/10.2801/75320)

Cedefop policy messages on inclusion

BRIEFING NOTE

Keeping young people in (vocational) education: what works?

Too many young people leave education (education) too soon. Yet early leavers are at high unemployment, poverty and crime, and now economy 1.25% of GDP. Can this flow be staunch

Source: Eurostat, labour force survey (extracted on 5/11/2019)

Who are the early leavers?

As they stand, early leaving rates across the EU are not strictly comparable.

- Not all countries end compulsory education at the same age; this varies between 15 and 18.
- For international comparisons, national statistics follow the Eurostat definition (18 to 24 year-olds who have completed only ISCED levels 2 and 3C, have no other qualifications, and have not been in education and training within the past four

- Inconsistent country. An considered an employer
- In some vocational dropouts programme.

BRIEFING NOTE

Vocational education and training prevent and counteracts early leaving from the education system

New findings shed light on the role vocational education and training play in attracting, retaining and reintegrating young people with different ability and learning backgrounds

It is well known that young people facing learning difficulty or failure, or belonging to vulnerable groups, such as migrants, are often pointed towards vocational education and training (VET) pathways. These include programmes for low performers and for pupils who prefer non-academic learning; they offer many young people a (second) chance to obtain a labour-market-relevant qualification (1).

Much less is known, however, about young leavers' individual trajectories. What type of education/training programme have they left? Why? How many of them return to education? How many chose vocational education and training as a second chance option? And how many graduate eventually? So far, European statistics have only allowed for a quantification of the overall phenomenon, neither distinguishing between early leaving from general and from vocational education, nor breaking early leavers down into categories (2). To close these gaps, Cedefop launched a four-year project in 2013, analysing secondary data from the OECD's programme for the international assessment of adult competences (PIAAC) and Eurostat's labour force and adult education surveys, as well as primary data collected from selected countries (3). The results of the project are expected to

provide a more differentiated basis for policy-makers in prevention, intervention or compensatory measures to address early leaving from education training.

Box 1. Tackling early leaving from education and training in Europe: strategies, policies and measures

More evidence – New insights

Vocational education and training programmes accommodate large numbers of returning learners who make a second education choice because they have either dropped out of (general) vocational education or decided to change learning pathway, often end up in vocational education and training. One third of those who have experienced dropout at upper secondary level subsequently take up a vocational training programme and ultimately obtain an upper or even post-secondary level qualification.

- (1) Keeping young people in (vocational) education: what works? Cedefop briefing note, No 9084, December 2013.
- (2) Meaningful categories of early leavers could be: non-starters (who have never taken up upper secondary VET), dropouts (who failed to complete a programme), and non-qualified learners (who have completed a programme without obtaining a qualification).
- (3) The first year of this research was coordinated with Euridice's work on early leaving from school and led to the publication of a joint report in autumn 2014: Tackling early leaving from education and training: strategies, policies and measures (Box 1).

BRIEFING NOTE

PREVENTING LOW SKILLS THROUGH LIFELONG LEARNING

Flexible learning pathways to keep youth at risk and low-skilled adults in education or work

In 2017, 15.7% of low-qualified aged 15 to 29 were not in training (NEET), compare educated peers. In the same rate of low-qualified adults stood at 13.9% in the EU; qualified peers was at 4.2%

Low skills, usually associated with economic cost. They are individuals concerned, their earnings, self-confidence, and in civil society (4). This is why increasingly being seen as early intervention, from offering low-skilled people and various upskilling in skills training.

Discover Cedefop's tools Cedefop's VET toolkit for which have helped young supports policy-makers an design, implement and evaluate

Cedefop's resources for general and policy-makers working toolkit on usage of labour practices; and training on how

- (1) All data from Eurostat: ec.europa.eu/eurostat
- (2) Low-qualified are individuals schooling corresponding to it they are compared to peers at Cedefop (2017). Interview in social cost of low-qualified adults

BRIEFING NOTE

MAINSTREAMING VET POLICIES ADDRESSING EARLY LEAVING FROM EDUCATION AND TRAINING

From projects and local initiatives to national programmes and policies

In 2014, the rate of early leaving from education and training in the EU had dropped to just one percentage point above the Europe 2020 benchmark of less than 10%. This encouraging trend is partly owed to the numerous projects and initiatives across Europe over the last three decades which have supported young people at risk of dropping out of education. Yet many of these initiatives have neither aroused attention nor found a market beyond their local context, in spite of their success. What has prevented policy makers and practitioners in other places reaping their benefits? What does it take to transfer successful practices and make them work in different settings?

Following analysis of the causes and manifestations of early leaving from education and training, and of policies preventing and counteracting the phenomenon (1), Cedefop has been looking at the conditions for mainstreaming successful projects and initiatives into regional/national programmes and for policy learning from one country to another. In its study on The role of VET in reducing early leaving from education and training (2), it has analysed numerous initiatives and policies, which have proven efficient in mitigating or eliminating early leaving risk factors, and identified their common key features.

A persistent challenge: obtaining conclusive evaluations

Evaluations of the effectiveness of policies addressing early leaving from VET are scarce in Europe. When they are carried out they often convey only a partial understanding of whether and why a given policy worked and of the benefits it offered to individual learners.

Cedefop has mapped over 300 different initiatives conducted in 36 European countries (3). Evidence of success is available for only 44 of these. Some have not been evaluated but underpinned by monitoring data providing some clues as to the number of participants and, at best, their pathways. Evaluations of the whole range of indicators showing the ultimate effect of a policy on retention and qualification attainment, which can serve to inform policy making, are more an exception than the rule. There is a need to promote an evaluation culture to build capacity enabling policy learning.

Cedefop video on the role of VET in combating early leaving with learners' testimonials on how VET has played a role in their decision to continue their studies and find a job.

(1) All countries which have participated in ET 2020 since 2014.

- (1) See Cedefop's previous briefing notes: <http://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/publications-and-resources/publications/9105> and <http://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/publications-and-resources/publications/9101>
- (2) Cedefop 2016, forthcoming. More information at <http://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/projects/projects/early-leaving-education-and-training>

BRIEFING NOTE

VOCATIONAL EDUCATION AND TRAINING AS A LIFE JACKET

Cedefop's work on VET supporting social inclusion of young NEETs

Young people not in employment, education or training (NEETs) are absent both from the labour market and the education sector, thus facing a high risk of professional, digital and social exclusion. Analyses of the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic show that, in spite of EU countries' bold response to this crisis protecting jobs, businesses and livelihoods, yet again, young people were hardest hit by its effects. This is why young NEETs have continued to be a top policy priority at national and EU levels.

The concept of NEETs as an individual risk group (e.g. compared to early leavers from education or long-term unemployed adults) emerged in the aftermath of the 2008 financial crisis, which had a devastating effect on young people's employment in the EU. The concept has allowed policy-makers and practitioners to tackle the effects of progressive marginalisation and prolonged inactivity of young people in a more targeted way.

YOUNG NEETs: WHO ARE THEY?

In the EU, young people with no or low qualifications are, on average, three times more likely to be NEETs than those with tertiary education; and twice as likely as those with secondary education. Other factors also play a role: living in a household with low income, being raised by a single parent, living in a rural area, being born in a country outside the EU, or having a disability. Young NEETs often suffer from poverty, social exclusion, insecurity, or health problems (1).

Beyond personal circumstances, labour market failures and mismatches often disproportionately affect young people. The results of a 2020 large-scale research project in Greece, funded by the European Economic Area, illustrate the dire employment situation of young Greeks: 15.9% were unemployed and actively looking

for a job, compared to 6.3% of their peers in the EU as a whole (2). The large number of young unemployed in Greece includes many well-qualified young people. Perceiving vocational education and training (VET) as a potential route to a job, many of them are willing to attend a training programme, provided it will help them (re)enter the labour market.

VET FOR EMPower YOUNG PEOPLE

In line with the principles of the European Pillar of Social Rights, VET, offering young people practical opportunities to obtain skills and acquire a qualification, is a powerful shield against marginalisation. According to the 2021 Council Resolution on a European education area by 2030, we are witnessing an increase in labour market needs for a different mix of skills and qualifications.

Being closely tied to the labour market, VET can react swiftly to skill needs as they emerge. For example, to keep pace with the digitalisation of the European economy, VET is incorporating a range of digital skills, responding both to occupation-specific and transversal skill needs. It is also central to policies supporting young NEETs, such as outreach, personalised guidance, and assessment and validation of their existing formal and informal skills. It is the role of policy-makers to ensure VET's labour market relevance and so help unlock its inclusive potential. VET programmes, with their practical component, can help young people acquire entrepreneurship skills and ease their transition to work. Ultimately, they can provide young people with skills harnessing their employability and fostering their inclusion in society.

(1) Broken down by gender, this corresponds to 14.6% of men and 17.4% of women aged 20-34 for Greece, compared to 6.6% of men and 5.8% of women of that age for the EU as a whole.

Cedefop supporting VET teachers & trainers to promote inclusion

Research paper

Teachers and trainers in a changing world

Building up competences for inclusive, green and digitalised vocational education and training (VET)
Synthesis report

DOI: [10.2801/53769](https://doi.org/10.2801/53769)

BRIEFING NOTE

EMPOWERING TEACHERS AND TRAINERS TO MANAGE CHANGE

VET teacher and trainer professional development is crucial to helping them perform their many tasks

Teachers and trainers are at the forefront of initial vocational education and training (VET) delivery (1). In the face of the unprecedented challenges created by the pandemic and the war in Ukraine, their commitment and creativity have been central to sustaining teaching and learning in schools and workplaces. They play a key role in empowering young people, on whose lives and hopes the lockdowns have taken a particularly high toll, and in helping integrate refugees into Europe's labour markets.

At the same time, the greening of European economies and the rapid digitalisation of many jobs, including the teaching profession itself, confront them with more new skills requirements. This is why it is now more important than ever for them to upgrade and update their own skills to be able, in turn, to instil (self-)confidence in their students, trainees and apprentices, as well as offering them up-to-date knowledge and skills. This briefing note presents new evidence gathered by Cedefop on teacher and trainer initial training and continuous professional development (CPD), including many practical examples (2).

Source: Cedefop.

The vocational training and labour market inclusion of young people not in employment, education or training (NEETs), of refugees, asylum seekers and other vulnerable groups has become a major focus. Today it is a cornerstone of high-quality VET⁽¹⁾, requiring specific psychosocial and intercultural skills from teachers and trainers.

- 1 While a few countries do not specifically define VET as opposed to continuing VET (e.g. Ireland, Finland, Slovakia), most consider it as a distinct pathway to a qualification and occupation providing young people an access route to the labour market.
- 2 The 2020 *Osaka Declaration* states that "excellent and inclusive European VET are equally necessary for the competitiveness of European enterprises and a well-functioning European labour market", highlighting that they are in fact the two sides of the same coin.

DOI: [10.2801/378686](https://doi.org/10.2801/378686)

RESEARCH PAPER No 47

Vocational pedagogies and benefits for learners: practices and challenges in Europe

DOI: [10.2801/294434](https://doi.org/10.2801/294434)

BRIEFING NOTE

PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT FOR VET TEACHERS AND TRAINERS

A guarantee of quality in vocational education and training

Committed and competent teachers and trainers are crucial to ensuring the quality and labour market relevance of learning, both in VET schools/centres and in companies, and whether in classrooms, in workshops, in labs and simulated learning environments, or at the workplace. Teachers and trainers are responsible for strengthening the links between education and work, establishing new curricula, providing more, and high-quality, apprenticeships and other forms of work-based learning, and applying the European tools. In the coming years, VET teachers and trainers will be required to help shape quick and flexible responses to emerging needs, related both to the integration of thousands of refugees and migrants into the labour market and to the need to develop basic, digital and entrepreneurial skills. Providing teachers and trainers with access to quality professional development and support is essential to ensuring that both their technical competences and pedagogical skills are up to the highest standards.

While VET teacher and trainer professional development has been on the EU education policy agenda for many years (3), it has not been sufficiently visible in national policies (4). The Riga conclusions (2015) have put renewed emphasis on the issue, calling for systematic approaches to and opportunities for initial and continuing professional development (CPD) of VET teachers, trainers and mentors. Cooperation and partnerships among stakeholders are seen as a way to support this.

(3) The *Bruges communiqué* (2010) had invited Member States to invest in and improve initial and continuing training for VET teachers and trainers by offering flexible training provision enabling them to:

- acquire the right set of competences;
- take up broader and more complex training-related tasks;
- deal with the increasing heterogeneity of learners;
- use new learning methods;
- make the most of new technologies.

(4) As stated in the Riga conclusions (2015).

DOI: [10.2801/37482](https://doi.org/10.2801/37482)

Giving voice to teachers to improve their professional development

The image shows a screenshot of the EVTS (European Vocational Teacher Survey) website. The header is dark blue with the EVTS logo and navigation links: HOME, ABOUT THIS SURVEY, DATA PROTECTION, FAQs, CONTACT, FOR SCHOOLS, FOR EXPERTS, and LANGUAGES. The main content area features a large blue heading 'Welcome to the European Vocational Teacher Survey!' and a prominent yellow button that says 'Click here to login and complete the survey'. Below the button, there is a paragraph of text: 'Your participation in the European Vocational Teacher Survey (EVTS) is critical to improving vocational education and'. To the right of the text, there are several circular images: one showing a woman with a clipboard, another showing hands working with a plant, and a third showing two people wearing safety helmets. There are also some light blue icons like a gear, a lightbulb, and a network diagram.

EVTS EUROPEAN VOCATIONAL TEACHER SURVEY

CEDEFOP
European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training

HOME ABOUT THIS SURVEY DATA PROTECTION FAQs CONTACT FOR SCHOOLS FOR EXPERTS LANGUAGES

Welcome to the European Vocational Teacher Survey!

[Click here to login and complete the survey](#)

Your participation in the European Vocational Teacher Survey (EVTS) is critical to improving vocational education and

<https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/projects/vocational-teacher-survey>

A close-up photograph of a person's hand typing on a laptop keyboard. The hand is in the foreground, and the keyboard is slightly out of focus in the background. The lighting is soft and natural.

Cedefop tools on inclusion

VET toolkit for tackling early leaving

www.cedefop.europa.eu/TEL-toolkit

VET toolkit for empowering NEETs

<https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/tools/neets>

VET toolkit for tackling early leaving

Source of support to policy makers and education and training providers

🇬🇧 BREXIT DISCLAIMER

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Intervene

Evaluate

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Submit your good practices and tools

Become an ambassador on tackling early leaving from VET

VET toolkit for tackling early leaving

Source of support to policy makers and education and training providers

UK BREXIT DISCLAIMER

Profiles at risk

Risk of early leaving

Learners at risk of early leaving

Learners escaping the system

Learners confronting the system

Learners disengaging due to difficulties adapting after transition

Learners disengaging because they cannot find a placement

Young people who left education and training because of caring, parenting or working obligations

Young people who left education and training and combine multiple disadvantage, possibly facing health and psycho-social issues

Young people not in employment, education or training (NEETs)

20 key Intervention approaches

Building motivation to learn

Show related protective factors ▾

Community involvement

Show related protective factors ▾

Comprehensive support to tackle complex needs

Show related protective factors ▾

Counselling to address barriers to learning

Show related protective factors ▾

Developing employability skills

Show related protective factors ▾

Digital inclusion and well-being

Show related protective factors ▾

Flexible education and training systems

Show related protective factors ▾

Guidance: supporting youth to manage their careers

Show related protective factors ▾

Identification of learners at risk of early leaving

Improving VET image and attractiveness

Show related protective factors ▾

Inclusive work-based learning environments

Show related protective factors ▾

Monitoring early leavers

One-to-one support through coaching or mentoring

Show related protective factors ▾

Practical application of theoretical courses

Show related protective factors ▾

Professional development for inclusive teaching and training

Show related protective factors ▾

Psychosocial support

Show related protective factors ▾

Second chance measures

Show related protective factors ▾

Tailored learning pathways

Show related protective factors ▾

Validation of non-formal and informal learning

Work-based learning and simulations

Show related protective factors ▾

VET toolkit for empowering NEETs

Source of support to young people not in employment, education or training

BROWSE BY

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Source of support to young people not in employment, education or training

Young people not in employment, education or training (NEETs)

Distance from participation in employment, education and training

SEEKING WORK AND/OR EDUCATION OR TRAINING

NOT SEEKING WORK AND/OR EDUCATION OR TRAINING

Re-entrants

NEETs in recent search

NEETs in long-term search

Unavailable due to family responsibilities

Unavailable due to illness or disability

Discouraged and disengaged young people

VET toolkit for empowering NEETs

Source of support to young people not in employment, education or training

Intervention approaches

- Easing transitions into work**
Show related risk factors ▾
- Flexible and permeable education and training systems**
Show related risk factors ▾
- Helping female NEETs (re)integrate into education, employment or training**
- Improving the appeal of VET**
Show related risk factors ▾
- Lifelong guidance: supporting NEETs to manage their careers**
Show related risk factors ▾
- Offering mentorship programmes to NEETs**
Show related risk factors ▾
- Outreach**
Show related risk factors ▾
- Skills development**
Show related risk factors ▾
- Validation of non-formal and informal learning**
Show related risk factors ▾

Ambassadors

Advanced search

**BECOME AN
AMBASSADOR**

VET toolkit for empowering NEETs

Source of support to young people not in employment, education or training

Join us in Brussels!

SHAPING LEARNING AND SKILLS FOR EUROPE

CEDEFOP 50TH ANNIVERSARY CONFERENCE

27 May 2025, Brussels

Youth in education, youth in employment

Boosting European policies
for social inclusion

18TH CEDEFOP BRUSSELS SEMINAR

23 June 2025
10.00-13.30 CET
Brussels

#CedefopBrusselsSeminar

VET4YOUTH TEAM

PROMOTING INCLUSIVE EXCELLENCE FOR YOUNG PEOPLE

Thank you

www.cedefop.europa.eu

@RenaPsifidou

Cedefop theme: VET for youth – Teachers and trainers

Cedefop's VET toolkit for tackling early leaving

Cedefop's VET toolkit for empowering NEETs

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